

The Impact of Motivation on Employees' Performance at Sulu State College

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Abstract

This descriptive-correlational study determines the impact of motivation on the employee's performance at Sulu State during the Academic Year 2023-2024. With 100 respondents, it employed frequency counts and percentages, weighted mean and standard deviation, t-test for independent samples one-way ANOVA, and Pearson's r . This study reveals the following findings: 1) Out of 100 employee-respondents, the majority are within 23-39 years old, are female employees, are married, have 5 years & below of length of service, have regular-permanent status of appointment, and have 11,999 & below of salary rate. 2) Generally, employee-respondents affirmed that factors such as Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship have high impact on employees' motivation at Sulu State College. 3) Generally, profile variables such as

age, civil status, status of appointment, length of service, and salary indeed intervene in ways how employee-respondents assess the extent of the impact of motivation 4) Employee-respondents who generally perceived the impact of motivation on the employees at Sulu State College in terms of Promotion as "Strongly Agree" are most probably the same group of respondents who perceived the impact of Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship as "Strongly Agree", respectively. 5) This study tends to support Abraham Maslow (1954) theory of motivation as expounded by Victor H. Vroom (1960) in his expectancy theory of motivation which assumes that motivation is high when workers believe that high level of effort leads to high performance and high-performance leads to the attainment of desired outcomes.

Keywords: *Employees, Motivation, Productivity, Organization, Performance*

INTRODUCTION

Employees are the heart of any organization. For any organization to operate smoothly and without any interruption, employee cooperation cannot be replaced with anything else. It is of utmost importance that the employees of an organization not only have a good relationship with the top management but also maintain a healthy and professional relationship with their coworkers. All organizations are concerned with

what should be done to achieve sustained high levels of performance through people. Consequently, the subject of adequate incentives for workers, as derived from the many attempts made by management practitioners, is to look for the best way to manage to accomplish an objective or mission with the least inputs of materials and human resources available.

Motivation is an employee's intrinsic enthusiasm about and drive to accomplish activities related to work. Motivation is that interior drive that causes a person to decide to act. An individual's motivation is influenced by biological, intellectual, social & emotional factors. Motivation is multifaceted; we cannot easily define motivation, an intrinsic driving force that can also be influenced by external factors. Every person has activities, events, people, and goals in his or her life that he or she finds motivating. By using intrinsic satisfaction & extrinsic factor organization can inspire employee motivation at work. Fulfilling the employees' needs and expectations from work and the workplace factors that enable employee motivation - or not. These variables make motivating employees challenging. Sometime employers fail to understand the importance of motivation in accomplishing their mission and vision. Even when they understand the significance of motivation, they lack the skill and knowledge to provide a work environment that fosters employee motivation.

Motivated employees are inclined to be more productive than non-motivated employees. Most businesses make some pains to motivate workers, but this is normally easier said than done. Employees are all individuals with different like's dislikes and needs, and different things will motivate each.

Certain problems of inadequate motivation however do arise as it concerns certain individuals who come into the work situation with differences in expectation, behavior, and outlook. These problems of individual motivation may be divided into two categories. Firstly, the inability of certain individuals to be motivated may stem from the fact that there is a deficiency in their personality. Maybe the desire to avoid failure may be too strong while paradoxically, the motive for producing positive results maybe too weak. This could produce a general resistance to achieving oriented activity that should naturally be overcome by other extrinsic modes of motivation if there is to be any spur to achievement-oriented activity at all. Secondly, even when the motive is relatively strong, the challenges before the individual worker may be proven to be inadequate or too difficult, whichever of these apply to the individual worker will usually manifest themselves in different ways such as lack of enthusiasm or premature surrender (Bryans and Cronin, 2019).

Despite all these apparent attendant problems of motivation and productivity, every organization does necessarily seek means of ensuring continuous productivity, which would be geared towards the accomplishment of organization goals.

Organizations that give little or no regard to the needs of their employees usually face many problems. A neglect of the employee's needs will make the employee reluctant to put his/her best at work. This will lead to a drop in efficiency and will further lead to a decline in the average output of employees. It is therefore very important for organization to take note of the needs of its employees and try as much as possible to cater for them and motivate them. Every employee is a rational being and so he acts the way he does for a reason. If therefore, the goals of an organization will be achieved it would need to understand the kind of motives that will prompt employees to act the way they do and provide ways of helping them to satisfy those needs as this will motivate them to put in their best. The researcher would want to know those motives that prompt workers to put in their best always and all the time in an organization. The researcher will also want to know what motivates employees to work well and provide ways of helping them to satisfy their needs. The researcher would want to know those motives that can prompt workers to always put their best in an organization or what will stop them from putting in their best.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to ascertain the impact of motivation on employees' performance at Sulu State College. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following question:

1. What is the demographic profile of the employees at Sulu State College in terms of:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Gender
 - 1.3 Educational Attainment
 - 1.4 Status of Appointment
 - 1.5 Length of service and
 - 1.6 Salary?
2. What is the extent of the effect of motivation impact on employees' performance at Sulu State College in terms of
 - 2.1 Promotion
 - 2.2 Job Satisfaction
 - 2.3 Work Environment, and
 - 2.4 Incentives?
3. Is there a significant difference in the impact of motivation of the employees' performance at Sulu State College in terms of
 - 3.1 Age
 - 3.2 Gender
 - 3.3 Educational Attainment
 - 3.4 Status of Appointment
 - 3.5 Length of service and
 - 3.6 Salary?
4. Is there a significant correlation to the impact of motivation of the Employees performance at Sulu State College in terms of:
 - 4.1 Promotion
 - 4.2 Job Satisfaction
 - 4.3 Work Environment, and
 - 4.4 Incentives?

Hypotheses of the Study

This study is anchored on the following research null hypotheses.

1. There is no significant difference in the impact of motivation of the employee's performance at Sulu State College when the responses are categorized according to the profile of the employees.
2. There is no significant correlation on the impact of motivation of the employee's performance at Sulu State College when the data are grouped according to the employees' profile.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate into the impact of motivation on Employees performance at Sulu State college, Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. To determine the demographic profile of respondents in terms of age; gender educational attainment, status of appointment, length of service and salary.
2. To determine the extent of the effect of impact of motivation on Employee's performance at Sulu State College in terms of promotion, job satisfaction, work environment, and incentives.
3. To determine the significant difference on the impact of motivation of the Employee's performance at Sulu State College in terms of age, gender, educational attainment, status of appointment, length of service and salary.
4. To determine the significant correlation on the impact of motivation of the Employees' performance at Sulu State College in terms of promotion, job satisfaction, work environment, and incentives.

Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on study of famous theorist of Motivation: Abraham Maslow (1954) on his study about the hierarchy of need of the employees. 2. Frederick Winslow Taylor (1856 – 1917) on his Theory of Scientific Management and 3. Victor H. Vroom on his study on motivation.

According to expectancy theory of motivation formulated by Victor H. Vroom in 1960, one of the first researchers to study motivation, posts that motivation is high when workers believe that high level of effort lead to high performance and high-performance leads to the attainment of desired outcomes. Expecting theory is one of the most popular theories of work motivation because it focuses on all three parts of the motivation equation: inputs, performance, and outcomes. This theory determines three major factors that lead to a person's motivation: expectancy, instrumentality, and valence.

Conceptual Framework

This study concerns the impact of motivation on the performance of employees. The employees have contributed to developing a positive school climate and support the school culture, provided they are motivated in their job.

This study investigated the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variables. Noted in the theories above, the administrative motivating factors can affect the employee's performance. In this study, the profile of the respondents is included in the independent variables. The employee's motivational factors are included in the dependent variables.

The important thing expressed in the figure below is that through motivation employees will put a lot of effort into increasing their outcome and performance and they will be satisfied. If motivation of employees is done perfectly, this will increase the employee loyalty, reduce conflict and enhance relationship and it will further increase employees' turnover and improve the relationship among the workforce which will encourage teamwork which will lead to maximum job satisfaction and with that employees will work towards achieving organizational goals which will lead to better organizational performance as shown in the conceptual paradigm in figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual Paradigm of the Study

Significance of the Study

The study has of great significance to the organization because there is a lot of competition all over the world. Organizations in different parts of this world are completing the resources that are available such as employees. So, to get the right number of employees, you want your organization to have a good image of retaining and motivating employees. The findings from this study will help to highlight those areas where there are problems among staff and thus will be of great benefit to the management of organizations and process owners.

Furthermore, the results of this study would hopefully be significant in the sense that it would enable both the management and the labor union to better understand how the various incentive packages could be harnessed to inspire staff to increase and sustain productivity.

The result of this study would help to further highlight the likely problems of frustration and how motivation can be used to either reduce or eliminate these problems amongst staff of the organization. The results from this study will help to highlight the concept of group dynamics and staff behavior to work. Through such an understanding, the administrative scope of the chief executive's official could be broadened, and this would put him in a better position to review and overhaul their orientation to administration in terms of better motivating staff and thus producing better results by fully utilizing the human resources potential available.

This study will also be of immense benefit to process owners in the human resources functions of the organizations. Also, labor union officials and representatives at the negotiation meeting will find it useful when putting together their "basket of needs," and it will assist management in these other areas:

- a) Design and put together welfare incentives for the workforce.
- b) Enables the organization to identify various types of needs and expectations of people at work.
- c) Outline different approaches to work motivation.
- d) Explain the meaning and underlying concept of motivation.

Furthermore, the administrators and employees in the other schools can utilize the result of this study to facilitate the impact of motivation on teacher's performance. The school administrators can realize the importance of employees' motivation to assist their performance toward productivity. The result of this study can aid develop the strong relationship between the school management and the faculty members by overcoming the existing barriers to becoming a supportive unit of the school administration.

The findings of the study may serve as an eye-opener for **administrators** to improve personnel management for quality delivery of service and better output. Identifying the indicators of morale may guide administrators in planning and implementing programs for employees. It is hoped that administrators create an environment in the organization that is stimulating and encouraging and set the stage for the development of morale among their employees.

The **employees**, who are beneficiaries of the findings of this study, may gain a deeper perspective of what and how they are doing as professionals. That is, they may stay in the profession because they consider it as a vocation and not as a job; that they continue to find fulfillment and personal growth from the challenges that their profession offers

The **researcher** may gain invaluable experiences and insights from this study. She hopes to acquire a better perspective of her profession and gain a more meaningful outlook about it. Researchers may use the findings of this study for further investigation along relevance and significance in institutional management.

Scope And Delimitation of the Study

The relationship between the administrative councils and their Employees is governed by what motivates them to work and the fulfillment they derive from it. The management needs to understand how to elicit the cooperation of staff and direct their performance to achieving the goals and objectives of the organization. This study is delimited to Sulu State College, Patikul site, Bangkal Patikul, Sulu. The workforce to be covered within the context of the study will include contracts of service, temporary, permanent, and management staff. This study is further delimited in terms of the organizational sub-sets of familiarity, concern and driving force as well as approach to work.

METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a blueprint that guides the researcher from the very inception of the scientific investigation until its very completion (Harris, 1979). Hence, this chapter will begin by explaining the research designs, research locale, respondents, sampling design, data gathering instrument, data gathering procedure, statistical treatment of data, and end with validity of the questionnaire.

Research Design

This study utilized the Descriptive method of research to conduct and gather data and information, for assessing the impact of motivation on employees' performance at Sulu State College. The researchers intend to use survey methods to generate relevant information for both primary and secondary sources of

data. Questionnaires were distributed to randomly selected employees of Sulu State College on the impact of motivation on employees' performance.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Sulu State College, Sulu. Particularly in the School of Graduate Studies, School of Agriculture, School of Arts and Sciences, School of Business Administration and Management, School of Computer Studies and Engineering, School of Education, School of Nursing and Senior High School.

Research Instrument

This study used a checklist questionnaire patterned from the study of John Thomas Husman (2007). There are two sets of questions: the first set inquired about the profile of the respondents; the second set was inquired about the Impact of Motivation on Teacher's Performance at Sulu State College.

Data Gathering Procedure

While gathering the empirical data, a letter duly approved by the Dean of the Graduate Studies will be sought. The researcher will then request a written permission from the President of Sulu State College before the questionnaires will be administered to the selected schools/departments. Upon receipt of the approval of the request, the researcher was personally give and retrieve the questionnaires to the respondents, specifically among the chosen eight (8) major schools, such as: School of Graduate Studies, School of Agriculture, School of Arts and Sciences, School of Business Administration and Management, School of Computer Studies and Engineering, School of Education, School of Nursing and Senior High School.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the employees of the eight (8) departments/schools of Sulu State College, both permanent, temporary, contract of service, and part-time employees were included.

The selected participant in the study is one hundred (100) employees of the eight (8) Schools at Sulu State College, Bangkal Patikul, Sulu. The participants in this study emphasized the Impact of Motivation on the Performance of Sulu State College.

Table 1. Distribution of Respondents According to School

SULU STATE COLLEGE	NUMBER OF STAFF
School of Graduate Studies	10
School of Agriculture	10
School of Arts and Sciences	10
School of Business Administration and Management	10
School of Computer Studies and Engineering	20
School of Education	20
School of Nursing	10
Senior High School	10

TOTAL	100
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Validity and Reliability

The issue of validity and reliability of the instruments were accounted to the work of John Thomas Husman (2007). Initially, the reliability of the questionnaire was found at Cronbach's Alpha for overall scales are .862 (very high) and correlation coefficients at .782 (highly correlated) for overall subscales.

Statistical Treatment of Data

The questionnaires were analyzed descriptively and inferentially by using SPSS *version 20* for the computation of raw data to answer the research questions. The first research question will be answered descriptively (frequency and percentage distribution) to determine the respondents' profile. The second question will be answered descriptively (mean and standard deviation) to the extent of the effect of impact of motivation on teachers' performance at Sulu State College

The third research question was answered inferentially using a t-test (male and female) to determine the significant difference of the responses and one-way ANOVA (educational attainment and length of service) to determine significant differences in the impact of motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College. If the t and F significant values $< .05$ means, there is significant difference when the responses will be analyzed inferentially.

The fourth research question will be answered inferentially by using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) to find out whether a significant correlation on the impact of motivation of the Teacher's performance at Sulu State College. If the sig. value of $r < 0.05$ means, there is a significant correlation on the impact of motivation of the Teacher's performance at Sulu State College.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This chapter showcases the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the data gathered for this study. Specifically, it presents the impact of motivation on employees' performance at Sulu State College School Year 2023-2024; It also deals with respondent's demographic profiles in terms of age, gender, civil status, status of appointment, length of service, and salary; the impact of motivation on employees' performance in terms of Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced conflict, and Improved fellowship; and the significant correlation and differences in these sub-categories when data are classified according to respondents' demographic profiles.

The following are the presentations, analyses and interpretations of results based on the proper scoring and statistical treatments of data gathered for this study that correspond to each of the research questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the employee-respondents at Sulu State College in terms of: 1.1 Age; 1.2 Gender; 1.3 Civil Status; 1.4 Length of Service; 1.5 Status of Appointment; and 1.6 Salary?

1.1 In terms of Age

Table 1.1 shows the demographic profile of employee-respondents in terms of age. It can be seen from this table that of the 100 employee-respondents, 22 (22.0%) are 22 years old & below, 38 (38.0%) are 23-39 years old, 22 (22.0%) are 40-49 years, and 18 (18.0%) are 50 years old & above. This study reveals

that more than one-third or most of the total respondents involved in this study are between 23-39 years old. This result implies that there is a considerable number of employees who have belonged to the middle cluster of age bracket as categorized in this study.

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of employee-respondents in terms of age

Age	Number of Respondents	Percent
22 years old & below	22	22.0%
23-39 years old	38	38.0%
40-49 years old	22	22.0%
50 years old & above	18	18.0%
Total	100	100%

1.2 In terms of Gender

Table 1.2 reflects the demographic profile of employee-respondents in terms of gender. It can be gleaned from this table that out of 100 employee-respondents, 38 (38.0%) are male, and 62 (62.0%) are female. This study reveals that nearly three-fourths, or the great majority, of the total respondents involved in this study are female employees. This result implies that the workforce of Sulu State College is predominated by the female gender.

Table 1.2 Demographic profile of teacher-respondents in terms of gender

Gender	Number of Respondents	Percent
Male	38	38.0%
Female	62	62.0%
Total	100	100%

1.3 In terms of Civil Status

Table 1.3 shows the demographic profile of employee-respondents in terms of civil status. This table reveals that of the 100 employee-respondents, 28 (28.0%) are single, 40 (40.0%) are married, and 32 (32.0%) are widowed/separated. This result reveals that nearly one-half of the employee-respondents involved in this study are married. This result implies that many of the employees at Sulu State College are dealing with their job, raising children and family, and tackling many other social, religious, and community activities.

1.4 In terms of Length of Service

Table 1.4 shows the demographic profile of employee-respondents in terms of length of service. This table reveals that of the 100 employee-respondents, 44 (44.0%) have 5 years & below, 24 (24.0%) have 5-10 years, and 32 (32.0%) have 11 years & above. This result reveals that nearly one-half of the employee-respondents involved in this study had 5 years & below length of service. This result implies that many of the teachers at Sulu State College have belonged to the lowest ladder of years of teaching experience as categorized in this study.

Table 1.3 Demographic profile of employee-respondents, in terms of length of service

Length of Service	Number of Respondents	Percent
5 years & below	44	44.0%
5-10 years	24	24.0%
11 years & below	32	32.0%
Total	100	100%

1.5 In terms of Status of Appointment

Table 1.5 shows the demographic profile of employee respondents in terms of the status of appointment. This table reveals that of the 100 employee-respondents, 5 (5.0%) are part-timers, 40 (40.00%) contract of service, 6 (6.0%) are temporary, and 49 (49.0%) have a regular-permanent status of appointment. This result reveals that nearly one-half of the employee-respondents involved in this study have a regular-permanent status of appointment. This result implies that, while many employees at Sulu State College have permanent appointment status, there are also an alarming number of employees who have contracts of service status.

Table 1.5 Demographic profile of employee-respondents, in terms of status of appointment

Status of Appointment	Number of Respondents	Percent
Part time	5	5.0%
Contract of Service	40	40.0%
Temporary	6	6.0%
Regular-Permanent	49	49.0%
Total	100	100%

1.6 In terms of Salary

Table 1.6 shows the demographic profile of employee-respondents in terms of salary. This table reveals that of the 100 employee-respondents, 46 (46.0%) have 11,999 & below, 7 (7.0%) have 12,000-24,000, 22 have 25,000-34,000, and 35 have 35,000 & above the salary rate. This result reveals that nearly one-half of the employees' respondents involved in this study have 11,999 & below of salary rate. This result implies that many employees at Sulu State College have the lowest salary rate, as categorized in this study.

Table 1.6 Demographic profile of employee-respondents in terms of salary

Salary	Number of Respondents	Percent
11,999 & below	46	46.0%
12,000-24,000	7	7.0%
25,000-34,000	22	22.0%

35,000 & above	25	25.0%
Total	100	100%

2. What is the extent of motivational effect on employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of: 2.1 Promotion; 2.2 Job Satisfaction; 2.3 Work Environment; 2.4 Incentives; 2.5 Loyalty; 2.6 Reduced conflict; and 2.7 Improved fellowship?

2.1 In the context of Promotion

Table 2.1 shows the extent of motivational effect on employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Promotion. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.6940 with a standard deviation of .39844 which is rated as "Strongly Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents involved in this study expressed strong agreement that employees at Sulu State College are satisfied with their academic ranks/positions, which eventually makes them happy and motivated to render efficient assignments.

It is worth noting that respondents rated the following items as "Strongly Agree", namely: "Makes me feel satisfied with my work with my present rank/position", "Makes me religiously report for work", "Inspires me to give 100% of my knowledge and skills", "I feel a sense of obligation to our organization", and "I feel committed to stay with the organization".

Table 2.1 Extent of the effect of motivation on Employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Promotion

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	It makes me feel satisfied with my work with my present rank/position.	4.6700	.56951	Strongly Agree
2	Makes me religiously report for work	4.6700	.53286	Strongly Agree
3	Inspires me to give 100% of my knowledge and skills.	4.7200	.45126	Strongly Agree
4	I feel a sense of obligation to our organization	4.7200	.47312	Strongly Agree
5	I feel committed to stay with the organization	4.6900	.52599	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.6940	.39844	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49= Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Partially Agree; (2) 1.50-2.49= Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Strongly Disagree

2.2 In the Context of Job Satisfaction

Table 2.2 shows the extent of motivational effects on employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Job Satisfaction. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.6780 with a standard deviation of .40291 which is rated as "Strongly Agree". This result indicates that employee-respondents involved in this study expressed strong agreement that the motivation they have through job satisfaction made a positive impact in their performance. They are satisfied and contented with the salary they have been receiving that commensurate to their respective ranks/positions.

Notably, respondents rated the following items as "Strongly Agree", namely: "Makes me feel satisfied with my work", "Encourages me to be contented with what I receive because of my work", "Makes

me proud to be part of the organization”, “My needs are satisfied by the compensation I received at work”, and “Help me to become very satisfied”.

Table 2.2: Extent of the effect of motivation on employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Job Satisfaction

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Makes me feel satisfied with my work	4.7400	.46319	Strongly Agree
2	Encourages me to be contented with what I receive because of my work.	4.6400	.55994	Strongly Agree
3	It makes me proud to be part of the organization	4.6700	.53286	Strongly Agree
4	My needs are satisfied by the compensation I received at work.	4.6100	.60126	Strongly Agree
5	Help me to become very satisfied	4.7300	.48938	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.6780	.40291	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49= Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Partially Agree; (2) 1.50-2.49= Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Strongly Disagree

2.3 In the Context of the Work Environment

Table 2.3 shows the extent of the effect of motivation on employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of the Work Environment. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.6420 with a standard deviation of .42096 which is rated as “Strongly Agree”. This result indicates that employee-respondents involved in this study expressed strong agreement that the motivation they have through the work environment resulted in a positive impact on their job performance. The positive work environment they have encourages them to perform to the best of their abilities.

Notably, respondents rated the following items as “Strongly Agree”, namely: “Motivates me to do my best because of the working condition that we have”, “Encourages me to work hard because of sufficient materials and supply available in the office”, “Keeps me from working beyond my office time”, “Keeps me from making unnecessary absence of work”, and “By being present at work at all the time, I can do more for the organization”.

Table 2.3 Extent of the effect of motivation on employee's performance at Sulu State College in the context of Work Environment

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Motivates me to do my best because of the working conditions that we have.	4.7500	.45782	Strongly Agree
2	Encourages me to work hard because of sufficient materials and supply available in the office	4.6300	.50562	Strongly Agree
3	Keeps me from working beyond my office time.	4.5600	.64071	Strongly Agree

4	Keeps me from making unnecessary absences of work.	4.530 0	.59382	Strongly Agree
5	By being present at work at all the time, I can do more for the organization.	4.740 0	.44084	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.642 0	.42096	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49= Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Partially Agree; (2) 1.50-2.49= Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Strongly Disagree

2.4 In the Context of Incentives

Table 2.4 shows the extent of motivational effect on employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Incentives. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.6800 with a standard deviation of .41194 which is rated as "Strongly Agree". This result indicates that employee-respondents involved in this study expressed strong agreement that the motivation they have through the incentives they are receiving led to a positive impact on their teaching performance. The provision of incentives encourages teachers to perform better beyond what is expected of their employees' performance.

Notably, respondents rated the following items as "Strongly Agree", namely: "Employee's needs are satisfied by the incentives they received at work", "Overtime work with pay is very much encouraging", "Employees are doing their best to give back to the organization", "Employees do not complain about their work in the organization", and "Employees are reporting on time for work".

Table 2.4 Extent of the effect of motivation on Employee's performance at Sulu State College in the context of Incentives

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Employees' needs are satisfied by the incentives they received at work	4.750 0	.5000 0	Strongly Agree
2	Overtime work with pay is very encouraging.	4.660 0	.5359 8	Strongly Agree
3	Employees are doing their best to give back to the organization	4.750 0	.4578 2	Strongly Agree
4	Employees do not complain about their work in the organization	4.600 0	.5504 8	Strongly Agree
5	Employees are reporting on time for work	4.640 0	.5777 0	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.680 0	.4119 4	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49= Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Partially Agree; (2) 1.50-2.49= Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Strongly Disagree

2.5 In the Context of Loyalty

Table 2.5 shows the extent of the effect of motivation on Employee's performance at Sulu State College in the context of Incentives. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.6480 with standard deviation of .42841 which is rated as "Strongly Agree". This result indicates that teacher-respondents involved in this study expressed strong agreement that the loyalty they have caused positive impact in their teaching performance. The fair treatment and recognition afforded by the administration encourages employees to serve the institution to the best of their abilities.

Notably, respondents rated the following items as “Strongly Agree”, namely: “Top management is fair treatment to all employees”, “Recognition for my hard work is highly implemented”, “Ongoing training necessary to perform my job well”, “It is not necessary to motivate employees before they perform”, and “Wages and salaries as a factor of motivation to gain loyalty”.

Table 2.5 Extent of the effect of motivation on Employee’s performance at Sulu State College in the context of Loyalty

	Statements	Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Top management is fair treatment for all employees.	4.7800	.41633	Strongly Agree
2	Recognition for my hard work is highly implemented.	4.6800	.52953	Strongly Agree
3	Ongoing training is necessary to perform my job well.	4.6800	.46883	Strongly Agree
4	It is not necessary to motivate employees before they perform.	4.4700	.70288	Strongly Agree
5	Wages and salaries as a factor of motivation to gain loyalty.	4.6300	.54411	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.6480	.42841	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49= Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Partially Agree; (2) 1.50-2.49= Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Strongly Disagree

2.6 In the Context of Reduced Conflict

Table 2.6 shows the extent of the effect of motivation on Employees’ performance at Sulu State College in the context of Reduced Conflict. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.6820 with standard deviation of .42744 which is rated as “Strongly Agree”. This result indicates that employee-respondents involved in this study expressed strong agreement that the friendly workplace they have due to reduced conflict caused a positive impact in their performance. Open communication channels, participation in decision making and mutual relationship among workers are encouraging factors for employees to stretch their muscles in serving the institution at the best level.

It is noteworthy that respondents rated the following items as “Strongly Agree”, namely: “There is a strong relationship between employee performance and motivation in the organization”, “Participation in Decision Making as Factor of Motivation to avoid conflict in the organization”, “Motivation of employees should not be limited to salaries and allowances”, “Failure to communicate will lead to a negative shift in any or all the above benefits”, and “Employees often endeavor to meet the set goals/objectives which attract bonus payments”.

Table 2.6 Extent of the effect of motivation on Employee`s performance at Sulu State College in the context of Reduced Conflict

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	There is a strong relationship between employee performance and motivation in the organization.	4.720 0	.473 12	Strongly Agree
2	Participation in Decision Making as Factor of Motivation to avoid conflict in the organization.	4.690 0	.506 42	Strongly Agree
3	The motivation of employees should not be limited to salaries and allowances.	4.710 0	.456 05	Strongly Agree
4	Failure to communicate will lead to a negative shift in any or all the above benefits.	4.600 0	.568 54	Strongly Agree
5	Employees often endeavor to meet the set goals/objectives which attract bonus payments.	4.690 0	.486 07	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.682 0	.427 44	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49= Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Partially Agree; (2) 1.50-2.49= Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Strongly Disagree

2.7 In the Context of Improved Fellowship

Table 2.7 shows the extent of the effect of motivation on Employee`s performance at Sulu State College in the context of Improved Fellowship. This category obtained a total weighted mean score of 4.6080 with standard deviation of .43291 which is rated as “Strongly Agree”. This result indicates that employee-respondents involved in this study expressed strong agreement that the collaboration among employees caused by improved fellowship resulted in a positive impact on employees` performance. Healthy relationships and support among employees are considered as motivating factors for employees to excel in their performance.

It is notable that respondents rated the following items as “Strongly Agree”, namely: “Good relationship with my co-workers is properly implemented”, “Deans/Supervisors in my work support employee development”, “Teamwork with my co-workers is very much observed”, “Employees do complain about their co-worker`s performance in the organization”, and “Opportunities are given to get better my skills for the job”.

Table 2.7 Extent of the effect of motivation on Employee`s performance at Sulu State College in the context of Improved Fellowship

Statements		Mean	S.D.	Rating
1	Good relationships with my co-workers are properly implemented.	4.8000	.47140	Strongly Agree
2	Deans/Supervisors in my work support employee development.	4.8100	.39428	Strongly Agree
3	Teamwork with my co-workers is very much observed.	4.6400	.57770	Strongly Agree

4	employees do complain about their co-workers' performance in the organization.	4.1600	.88443	Agree
5	Opportunities are given to get better my skills for the job.	4.6300	.54411	Strongly Agree
Total Weighted Mean		4.6080	.43291	Strongly Agree

Legend: (5) 4.50-5.00= Strongly Agree; (4) 3.50-4.49= Agree; (3) 2.50- 3.49= Partially Agree; (2) 1.50-2.49= Disagree; (1) 1.00- 1.49= Strongly Disagree

3. Is there a significant difference on the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employee's performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of: 3.1 Age; 3.2 Gender; 3.3 Civil Status; 3.4 Length of Service; 3.5 Length of service; and 3.6 Salary?

3.1 According to Age

Table 3.1 illustrates the difference in the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employee's performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age. It is reflected in this table that, except for "Job Satisfaction", "Work Environment", and "Reduced Conflict", all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance with their corresponding F-values and probability values are indeed significant at alpha .05. Table 3.1 Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age.

A Post Hoc Analysis using the Tukey Test was conducted to determine which groups classified according to respondents' age have different levels of mean in areas Promotion, Incentives, Loyalty, and Improved fellowship when data are grouped according to respondents' demographic profile in terms of age.

The result of the analysis, which is shown in Table 3.1.1, indicates that the difference in the means of Promotion, Incentives, Loyalty, and Improved fellowship is obtained by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On Incentives: It shows that the group of 50 Years & Above obtained the mean difference of -.30175* with Standard Error of .11430 and p-value of .047, which is significant at alpha=.05 over the 23 Years old & above group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance in terms of Incentives than those teacher-respondents with 50 years old & above.

On Loyalty: It shows that the group of 24-39 Years Old obtained the mean difference of .28852* with a Standard Error of .11001 and a p-value of .049, which is significant at alpha=.05 over the 23 Years old & below group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of motivation on the employee's performance in terms of Loyalty than those teacher-respondents with 23-39 years old & above.

On Improved Fellowship: It shows that the group of 50 Years Old & Above obtained the mean difference of -.35088* with Standard Error of .11766 and p-value of .0i9, which is significant at alpha=.05 over the 24-39 Years old group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance in terms of Improve50 years old & above.

A Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Promotion, Incentives, Loyalty, and Improved fellowship when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of age

3.2 According to Gender

Table 3.2 illustrates the difference in the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender. It is reflected in this table that, except for "Improved Fellowship," all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the impact of motivation of the Employee's performance with their corresponding Mean Differences, t-values, and probability values are not significant at alpha .05.

Table 3.2 Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of gender

3.3 According to Civil Status

Table 3.3 illustrates the difference in the extent of motivation's impact on the employees' performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of civil status. It is reflected in this table that all the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of motivation on the Teacher's performance with their corresponding F-values and probability values are indeed significant at alpha .05. Table 3.3 Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation of the Employee's performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of civil status

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey Test was conducted to determine which among groups classified according to respondents' civil status to have different levels of mean in areas Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship when data are grouped according to respondents' demographic profile in terms of civil status.

The result of the analysis, which is shown in Table 3.3.1, indicates that the difference in the means of Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On Promotion: It shows that the group of Married Status obtained the mean difference of $-.31019^*$ with Standard Error of $.07473$ and p-value of $.000$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Single Status group

On Job Satisfaction: It shows that the group of Married Status obtained the mean difference of $-.30465^*$ with Standard Error of $.07591$ and p-value of $.000$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Single Status group.

On Work Environment: It shows that the group of Married Status obtained the mean difference of $-.32713^*$ with Standard Error of $.07885$ and p-value of $.000$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Single Status group.

Incentives: It shows that the group of Married Status obtained the mean difference of $-.33308^*$ with Standard Error of $.07671$ and p-value of $.000$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Single Status group.

On Loyalty: It shows that the group of Married Status obtained the mean difference of $-.23161^*$ with Standard Error of $.08388$ and p-value of $.019$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Single Status group.

On Reduced Conflict: It shows that the group of Married Status obtained the mean difference of $-.22180^*$ with Standard Error of $.08407$ and p-value of $.026$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Single Status group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the motivational impact on the employees' performance in terms of Reduced Conflict than those employee-respondents with married status.

On Improved Fellowship: It shows that the group of Married Status obtained the mean difference of $-.32872^*$ with Standard Error of $.08132$ and p-value of $.000$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Single Status group.

A Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of the motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of civil status

3.4 According to Length of Service

The difference in the extent of motivational impact on the employees' performance at Sulu State College is when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of length of service. It is reflected in this table that, except for "Work Environment", "Loyalty" and "Improved Fellowship" all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of motivation on the Teacher's performance with their corresponding F-values and probability values are indeed significant at $\alpha .05$. This means that, although respondents in this study vary in length of service, still they indeed differ in their assessment of the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance. This result implies that a respondent who has 11 years & of years of teaching experience may probably make him/her a better perceiver of the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance over those who have 5 years & below of length of service, or vice versa.

The Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of length of service

A Post Hoc Analysis using the Tukey Test was conducted to determine which groups classified according to respondents' length of service have different levels of meaning in areas Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Incentives, and Reduced Conflict when data are grouped according to respondents' demographic profile in terms of length of service.

The result of the analysis, which is shown in Table 3.4.1, indicates that the difference in the means of Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Incentives, and Reduced Conflict by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On Promotion: It shows that the group of 11 Years & Above obtained the mean difference of $-.24545^*$ with Standard Error of $.08995$ and p-value of $.020$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the 5 years & Below group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance in terms of Promotion than those employee-respondents with 11 years & above years in service.

On Job Satisfaction: It shows that the group of 11 Years & Above obtained the mean difference of $-.26648^*$ with Standard Error of $.09049$ and p-value of $.011$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the 5 years & Below group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance in terms of job Satisfaction than those employee-respondents with 11 years & above of years in service.

On Incentives: It shows that the group of 11 Years & Above obtained the mean difference of $-.30852^*$ with Standard Error of $.09098$ and p-value of $.003$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the 5 years & Below group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have

better ways of assessing the extent of motivation on the employee's performance in terms of job Incentives than those employee-respondents with 11 years & above of years in service.

Table 3.4.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employee's performance at Sulu State College in the context of Promotion, Job Satisfaction, and Incentives when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of length of service

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Length of Service	(J) Grouping by Length of Service	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
<i>Promotion</i>	5 years & below	6-10 years	-.04545	.09824	.889
		11 years & above	-.24545*	.08995	.020
<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	5 years & below	6-10 years	-.06439	.09883	.792
		11 years & above	-.26648*	.09049	.011
<i>Incentives</i>	5 years & below	6-10 years	-.03561	.09937	.932
		11 years & above	-.30852*	.09098	.003

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.5 According to Status of Appointment

Table 3.5 illustrates the difference in the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employee's performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of status of appointment. It is reflected in this table that, except for "Promotion", "Reduced Conflict", and "Improved Fellowship" all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance with their corresponding F-values and probability values are indeed significant at alpha .05. This means that, although respondents in this study vary in status of appointment, still they indeed differ in their assessment of the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance. This result implies that a respondent who has a regular/permanent status of appointment may probably be/her better perceiver of the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance over those who respondents who have part-time, temporary, casual/contract of service, or vice versa.

The Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation on the employees' performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of status of appointment

A Post Hoc Analysis using the Tukey Test was conducted to determine which groups classified according to respondents' status of appointment have different levels of meaning in areas Job Satisfaction, Reduced Conflict, when data are grouped according to respondents' demographic profile in terms of length of service.

The result of the analysis, which is shown in Table 3.5.1, indicates that the difference in the means of Job Satisfaction, Incentives, and Reduced Conflict is by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On job Satisfaction: It shows that the group of Regular Status obtained the mean difference of $-.60245^*$ with a Standard Error of $.18080$ and a p-value of $.007$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Part Time group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the motivational impact on the employees' performance in terms of Job Satisfaction than those employee-respondents with a regular/permanent status of appointment.

On Incentives: It shows that the group of Regular Status obtained the mean difference of $-.59837^*$ with Standard Error of $.18569$ and p-value of $.009$, which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Part Time group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the impact of motivation on the employee's performance in terms of Incentives than those employee-respondents with regular/permanent status of appointment.

On educed Conflict: It shows that the group of Regular Status obtained the mean difference of $-.52000^*$ with Standard Error of $.19805$ and p-value of $.049$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the Part Time group. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of motivation on the employee's performance in terms of Reduced Conflict than those employee-respondents with regular/permanent status of appointment.

Table 3.5.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation of the employees' performance at Sulu State College in the context of Job Satisfaction, Incentives, and Reduced Conflict when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of status of appointment

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Status of Appointment	(J) Grouping by Status of Appointment	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
<i>Job Satisfaction</i>	Part-time	Contract of Service	$-.59500^*$.18267	.008
		Temporary	$-.41333$.23319	.293
		Regular	$-.60245^*$.18080	.007
<i>Incentives</i>	Part-time	Contract of Service	$-.60000^*$.18762	.010
		Temporary	$-.44667$.23951	.250
		Regular	$-.59837^*$.18569	.009
<i>Reduced Conflict</i>	Part-time	Contract of Service	$-.52000^*$.19805	.049
		Temporary	$-.29333$.25282	.653
		Regular	$-.44163$.19601	.117

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

3.6 According to Salary

Table 3.5.1 illustrates the difference in the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employee's performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of salary. It is reflected in this table that, except for "Loyalty", all other sub-categories subsumed under the extent of impact of motivation on the employee's performance with their corresponding F-values and probability values are indeed significant at $\alpha .05$. This means that, although respondents in this study

vary in their salary rate, still they indeed differ in their assessment of the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance. This result implies that a respondent who receives 35,000 and above may probably make him/her better perceiver toward the extent of motivation on the Employees' performance over those who receive 11,999 and below, 12,000 to 24,999, and 25,000 to 34,999, or vice versa.

Hence, it is safe to say that variable salary has indeed significant intervention in the ways how respondents assess the extent of impact of motivation on the Employee's performance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that "There is no significant difference in the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employee's performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of salary" is rejected.

The Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation of the Employee's performance at Sulu State College when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of salary

A Post Hoc Analysis using Tukey Test was conducted to determine which groups classified according to respondents' salary to have different levels of mean in areas Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship when data are grouped according to respondents' demographic profile in terms of length of service.

The result of the analysis which is shown in Table 3.6.1 indicates that the difference in the means of Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship by way of lower group means minus higher group means.

On job Satisfaction: It shows that the group receiving 35,000 & above obtained the mean difference of $-.43086^*$ with Standard Error of $.16406$ and p-value of $.049$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group receiving 12,000-24,000. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of motivation's impact on the employees' performance in terms of Promotion than those employee-respondents with salary of 35,000 & above.

On Work Environment: It shows that the group receiving 35,000 & above obtained the mean difference of $-.57943^*$ with Standard Error of $.17193$ and p-value of $.006$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group receiving 12,000-24,000. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of motivation impact on the employee's performance in terms of the Work Environment than those teacher-respondents with salary of 35,000 & above.

On Incentives: It shows that the group receiving 35,000 & above obtained the mean difference of $-.25617^*$ with Standard Error of $.09757$ and p-value of $.049$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group receiving 12,000-24,000. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of motivational impact on the employee's performance in terms of Incentives than those teacher-respondents with salary of 35,000 & above.

On Reduced Conflict: It shows that the group receiving 35,000 & obtained the mean difference of $-.38218^*$ with Standard Error of $.11993$ and p-value of $.010$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group receiving 12,000-24,000. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the extent of the motivational impact on the teachers' performance in terms of Reduced Conflict than those teacher-respondents with salary of 35,000 & above.

On Improved Fellowship: It shows that the group receiving 35,000 & above obtained the mean difference of $-.36000^*$ with Standard Error of $.12303$ and p-value of $.022$ which is significant at $\alpha=.05$ over the group receiving 12,000-24,000. So, under this sub-category, no other groups of respondents are supposed to have better ways of assessing the impact of motivation on the employee's performance in terms of Improved Fellowship Conflict than those teacher-respondents with salary of 35,000 & above.

Table 3.6.1 Post Hoc Analysis: Differences in the extent of the impact of motivation of the Employee's performance at Sulu State College in the context of Promotion, Work Environment, Incentives, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship when data are grouped according to their demographic profile in terms of salary

Dependent Variables	(I) Grouping by Salary	(J) Grouping by Salary	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	Sig.
<i>Promotion</i>	12,000-24,000	11,999 & below	-.21677	.15565	.507
		25,000-34,000	-.13377	.16649	.853
		35,000 & above	-.43086*	.16406	.049
Work Environment	12,000-24,000	11,999 & below	-.42360	.16312	.052
		25,000-34,000	-.33506	.17447	.226
		35,000 & above	-.57943*	.17193	.006
Incentives	11,999 & below	12,000-24,000	.21925	.15931	.517
		25,000-34,000	.07510	.10179	.882
		35,000 & above	-.25617*	.09757	.049
Reduced Conflict	25,000-34,000	11,999 & below	-.22253	.10635	.163
		12,000-24,000	-.03247	.17803	.998
		35,000 & above	-.38218*	.11993	.010
Improved Fellowship	25,000-34,000	11,999 & below	-.21739	.10909	.198
		12,000-24,000	-.25714	.18263	.497
		35,000 & above	-.36000*	.12303	.022

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

4. Is there a significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of motivation of the Employees at Sulu State College?

Table 4 illustrates the correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of motivation of the Employees at Sulu State College. It can be gleaned from this table that the computed Pearson Correlation Coefficients (Pearson's r) between these variables are all significant at alpha .05.

Specifically, the degree of correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of motivation of the Employees at Sulu State College is as follows:

- 1) High positive correlation between Promotion and Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship.
- 2) High positive correlation between Job Satisfaction and Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship.
- 3) High positive correlation between Work Environment and Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship.
- 4) High positive correlation between Incentives and Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship.
- 5) high positive correlation between Loyalty and Reduced Conflict and Improved Fellowship; and
- 6) High positive correlation between Reduced Conflict and Improved Fellowship.

These results indicate that the respondents who generally perceived the impact of motivation of the Employees at Sulu State College in terms of Promotion as “Strongly Agree” are most probably the same group of respondents who perceived the impact of Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship as “Strongly Agree”, respectively.

Hence, it is safe to say that, generally the impact of motivation of the Employees at Sulu State College is highly correlated.

Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, “There is no significant correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of motivation of the Employees at Sulu State College” is rejected.

The Correlation between the sub-categories subsumed under the impact of motivation on the Employees’ performance at Sulu State College

Summary of Findings

The following are findings of this study:

1) On demographic profile of respondents.

Out of the 100 employee-respondents, majority are within 23-39 years old, are female employees, are married, have 5 years & below of length of service, have regular-permanent status of appointment, and have 11,999 & below of salary rate.

2) On the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employees.

Sub-categories subsumed under the impact of motivation on the Employees at Sulu State College as Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship are all rated as “Strongly Agree” which means that have high impact on teachers’ motivation.

3) On differences in extent of the impact of motivation on the Employees.

Except for gender, there is a significant difference in extent of the impact of motivation on the Employees of Sulu State College when data are grouped according to gender. Employees who are 50 years old & above, who are married, with 11 years & above of years in service, with regular/permanent status of appointment, and with a salary of 35,000 & above are better perceivers of the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employees.

4. On correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employees.

Generally, there is a high positive correlation among the sub-categories subsumed under the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employees. Respondents who generally perceived the impact of motivation on the Employees at Sulu State College in terms of Promotion as “Strongly Agree” are most probably the same group of respondents who perceived the impact of Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship as “Strongly Agree”, respectively.

Conclusions

This study concludes the following:

- 1) In this study, employee-respondents are adequately represented in terms of age, gender, civil status, status of appointment, length of service, and salary.
- 2) Generally, employee-respondents affirmed that factors such as Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship have high impact on employees' motivation at Sulu State College.
- 3) Generally, profile variables such as age, civil status, status of appointment, length of service, and salary indeed intervene in ways how employee-respondents assess the extent of the impact of motivation on the Employees.
- 4) Employee-respondents who generally perceived the impact of motivation on the Employees at Sulu State College in terms of Promotion as "Strongly Agree" are most probably the same group of respondents who perceived the impact of Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship as "Strongly Agree", respectively.
- 5) This study tends to support Abraham Maslow (1954) theory of motivation as expounded by Victor H. Vroom (1960) in his expectancy theory of motivation which assumes that motivation is high when workers believe that high levels of effort lead to high performance and high performance leads to the attainment of desired outcomes.

Recommendations

This study recommends the following:

- 1) To ensure efficient delivery of employees' performance, academic leaders of Sulu State College should sustain the establishment of programs and policies that cater to the professional development of employees in terms of the fair implementation of the motivational factors such as Promotion, Job Satisfaction, Work Environment, Incentives, Loyalty, Reduced Conflict, and Improved Fellowship.
- 2) Employees should be continuously provided with updated training programs on technological advancement and skills.
- 3) Employees should be encouraged to continue upgrading their educational qualifications by pursuing graduate studies in their field of specialization.
- 4) Moreover, student-researchers in the field of administration and supervision are encouraged to conduct study like this one but to include other variables such as work environment, employees' strategies, employees' work attitudes, and employees' morale in some other settings.

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